

Analytical data on *A. pinnata*. De La Salle University, Manila, Philippines.

Analysis	Method ^a	Percentage ^b
Ash		20.0
Moisture		11.0
	SP	0.015
N	Kjeldahl	3.50
Mg	AA	0.60
K	Flame emission	3.8
Ca	AA	0.60
Mn	AA	0.13
Fe	AA	0.90
Zn	AA	0.01
As	AA	0.01
As	Gutzeib (UV-vis)	ND
Mo	AA	5 × 10 ⁻⁴
Hg	Flameless AA	ND
Pb	AA	ND
PO ₄	SP	0.56
SO ₄	Turbidimetric	1.40

^a SP = spectrophotocalorimetric, AA atomic absorption. ^b ND = nondetectable.

TG and DTA of azolla. A = *A. pinnata*, B = *A. microphylla*.

loss occurs. In the second, organic components are lost, followed by decarbonization and decomposition of inorganic sulfides and carbonates. The subsequent stages yield inorganic residue. The similarities in the TG-DTA curves of *A. pinnata* and *A. microphylla* indicate that the basic matrix is similar (see figure). *A. pinnata* exhibits weight losses of 12.42, 42.55, 62.13, and 78.30% in the temperature range 80-110, 210-320, 330-425, and 435-490 °C, respectively. *A. microphylla* shows 12.15, 44.93, 66.39, and 83.40% respectively in the range 75-110, 215-315,

325-420, and 440-490 °C. The exothermic peak temperatures in the DTA curve are at 287, 305, 358, and 460 °C for *A. pinnata* and 283, 310, 353,

and 460 °C for *A. microphylla*. The first and fourth peaks indicate the major decomposition process; the second and third peaks are less intense. □

Rice-based Cropping Systems

Response of transplanted rice to micronutrients and the residual effect on wheat

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We studied the effect of Zn, Mn, Cu, and Fe sulfates on yield of transplanted rice Pratap in the 1985 wet season and yield of wheat in the 1985-86 winter season. The soil and foliar applications of the micronutrients were compared with 5 t farmyard manure (FYM)/ ha containing 54% moisture.

Soil was silty clay loam (Typic Haplaquept) with pH 8.3, 1.303% organic matter, EC 0.22 dS/m, cation exchange capacity 24.5 meq/100 g soil, and DTPA-extractable Zn, Mn, Cu, and Fe at 0.80, 15.0, 0.18, and 15.5 mg/kg soil, respectively. FYM contained 0.45% N, 0.10% P, 0.35% K, and 40,200, 69, and 1,500 mg Zn, Mn, Cu, and Fe, respectively, /kg (oven dry

basis). Treatments were replicated three times in a randomized block design. Both crops received 80-17.4-33.3 kg NPK/ha in all treatments.

Soil and foliar applications of Zn and Cu increased rice yields significantly (see table). FYM with its micronutrients also increased rice yield significantly. Wheat yield was not significantly influenced by any treatment. □

Efficiency of complex fertilizers in a rice - rice farming system

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We evaluated four N sources in a randomized block design with four replications during the 1984 dry season (DS) and 1985 wet season (WS). Soil was lateritic sandy loam (pH 5.7, EC 0.115 dS/m, 0.680% organic carbon, 18 kg available P, and 150 kg available K/ ha. Rice variety Daya (120 d) was transplanted at 15- × 10-cm spacing. The recommended dose of 60-13-25 kg NPK/ha was applied through complex mixtures A and B (18-7.86-5 kg NPK/100 kg mixture) produced by Hari Fertilizer Factory, Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh, India; urea; and calcium ammonium nitrate plus P and K. N is in the form of NH₄Cl in mixture A and (NH₄)₂SO₄ in mixture B. The shortfall in N and K were adjusted with urea and muriate of potash. All P and K were applied at transplanting. Treatments received 50% N at transplanting, 25% at tillering, and 25% at panicle initiation.

Grain yield was highest with N as NH₄Cl (3.8 t/ha) (see table). N as

Direct and residual effects of micronutrients on rice and wheat yields. Keonjhar, Orissa, India, 1985-86.

Treatment	Application method	Grain yield (t/ha)	
		Rice	Wheat
Control		3.0	1.8
FYM 5 t/ha		3.2	1.9
Zn 4.5 kg/ha	Soil	3.3	1.7
Zn 0.11 mg/liter	Foliar	3.2	2.0
Mn 14.2 kg/ha	Soil	3.0	1.6
Mn 0.18 mg/liter	Foliar	3.1	1.6
Cu 2.5 kg/ha	Soil	3.2	1.8
Cu 0.07 mg/liter	Foliar	3.1	1.5
Fe 10 kg/ha	Soil	2.9	1.5
Fe 0.10 mg/liter	Foliar	3.0	1.8
CD (0.05)		0.1	ns

Effect of fertilizer mixtures on yield and yield attributes. Bhubaneswar, India, 1984-85.

Treatment	Panicle-bearing tillers/hill		Grains/panicle		1,000-grain wt (g)		Grain yield (t/ha)	
	DS	WS	DS	WS	DS	WS	DS	WS
Mixture A	5.3	5.0	82	70	22.8	24.0	3.8	2.8
Mixture B	4.3	4.2	81	68	22.4	24.1	3.5	2.5
Urea	4.0	4.0	71	67	22.0	23.5	3.1	2.2
Calcium ammonium nitrate	3.9	3.8	75	63	21.9	23.5	3.0	2.3
Control (no N)	3.5	3.3	72	62	21.8	23.4	2.8	2.0
CD (0.05)	0.6	0.6	1.3	1.7	ns	0.5	0.5	0.2

(NH₄)₂SO₄ was better than urea and calcium ammonium nitrate in DS and equal in WS. Panicle-bearing tillers/ hill, grain number/panicle, and test weight were higher with mixtures A and B, contributing directly to higher grain yield. □

Individuals, organizations, and media are invited to quote or reprint articles or excerpts from articles in the IRRN.

Announcements

Breeding for disease resistance in rice

Authors: S. Gangopadhyay and S. Y. Padmanabhan. 1987. 340 p., hardbound, 939 references, subject index. Price: Rs. 96.00. ISBN 81-204-0198-0

The authors of this book have synthesized published information on major rice diseases. They describe symptomatology, etiology, morphological and physiological variations of pathogens, pathogenic variability, types of varietal resistance, biochemical and anatomical traits of varieties in relation to resistance, genetics of resistance, and methods and strategies in breeding for resistance to various rice diseases with special emphasis on the blast pathogen.

Send orders to the publisher: Oxford & IBH Publishing Co., 66 Janpath, New Delhi 110001, India, or Park Hotel Bldgs., 17 Park Street, Calcutta 700016, India. □

Newsletter published for CRIN

A bulletin of the Caribbean Rice Improvement Network (CRIN) has been initiated. Vol. 1, no. 1, was published in Jun 1987 by Manuel J. Rosero, IRRI liaison scientist and network coordinator.

CRIN is coordinated through the Centro Internacional de Agricultura Tropical rice program with participation of IRRI-IRTP and Secretaria de Estado de Agricultura of the Dominican Republic and funded by the Canadian International Development Agency, International Development Research Centre, and the United Nations Development Programme.

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The wetlands and rice in subsaharan Africa

The proceedings of the international conference on wetland utilization for rice production in subsaharan Africa, 4-8 Nov 1985, in Ibadan, Nigeria, has been published by the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture. The volume includes 25 papers presented at the conference.

Major sections are Wetlands in subsaharan Africa, Water management, Improvement of rice varieties, Crop protection and nutrition, Cropping systems, Mechanization, and Transfer of technology.

Place orders for *The wetlands and rice in subsaharan Africa*, 318 p., with IITA, PMB 5320, Ibadan, Nigeria. □